

Table 1: Baseline characteristics by neuropsychiatric symptom status

	No Depression (N=426)	Depression (N=64)	p value	No Anxiety (N=379)	Anxiety (N=111)	p value	No Anxiety or Depression (N=362)	Comorbid Anxiety and Depression (N=47)	p value
Age at baseline			0.506			0.335			0.759
Mean (SD)	62.44 (9.41)	61.60 (9.53)		62.55 (9.38)	61.57 (9.56)		62.60 (9.33)	61.65 (9.21)	
Male gender, n (%)	282 (66.2%)	40 (62.5%)	0.561	251 (66.2%)	71 (64.0%)	0.659	239 (66.0%)	28 (59.6%)	0.791
Race, n (%)			0.003			0.539			0.020
White	397 (94.5%)	54 (84.4%)		349 (93.6%)	102 (91.9%)		335 (94.1%)	40 (85.1%)	
Non-white	23 (5.5%)	10 (15.6%)		24 (6.4%)	9 (8.1%)		21 (5.9%)	7 (14.9%)	
Unknown	6	0		6	0		6	0	
Education in years			0.035			0.106			0.167
Mean (SD)	15.87 (3.05)	15.02 (2.87)		15.88 (3.05)	15.35 (2.99)		15.90 (3.07)	14.87 (3.00)	
MDS-UPDRS Part 1			< 0.001			<0.001			<0.001
Mean (SD)	5.00 (3.40)	9.56 (6.03)		5.07 (3.63)	7.41 (5.14)		4.89 (3.41)	9.83 (6.17)	
MDS-UPDRS Part 2			< 0.001			0.020			0.001
Mean (SD)	5.46 (4.05)	7.66 (4.83)		5.51 (4.18)	6.57 (4.28)		5.42 (4.15)	7.72 (4.94)	
MDS-UPDRS Part 3			0.074			0.033			0.077
Mean (SD)	20.77 (8.98)	22.89 (7.77)		20.59 (8.91)	22.62 (8.48)		20.63 (9.01)	24.04 (7.90)	
MDS-UPDRS Total			< 0.001			<0.001			<0.001
Mean (SD)	31.24 (12.66)	40.11 (14.93)		31.16 (12.78)	36.60 (14.20)		30.94 (12.77)	41.60 (15.57)	
Schwab England			0.029			0.038			0.086
Mean (SD)	93.88 (5.81)	92.19 (5.70)		93.96 (5.80)	92.66 (5.79)		93.98 (5.87)	91.70 (6.10)	
MoCA<26			0.149			0.211			0.031
Mean (SD)	92 (21.6%)	19 (29.7%)		81 (21.4%)	30 (27.0%)		73 (20.2%)	11 (23.4%)	
Cognitive Impairment			0.179			0.015			0.083
No, Mean (SD)	290 (85.3%)	43 (78.2%)		258 (86.9%)	75 (76.5%)		246 (86.6%)	31 (73.8%)	
Yes, Mean (SD)	50 (14.7%)	12 (21.8%)		39 (13.1%)	23 (23.5%)		38 (13.4%)	11 (26.2%)	

MDS-UPDRS, Movement Disorders Society – Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale